

D3.2

Interactions with other projects dataspace: how and why - algorithms and architectural approach to be considered in DATA CELLAR CIM

PROJECT: DATA CELLAR, GRANT AGREEMENT No. 101069694

ORGANISATION NAME OF LEAD CONTRACTOR: RINA-C

Project Contractual Details

Project Title	Data hub for the Creation of Energy communities at Local Level and to Advance Research on them
Project Acronym	DATA CELLAR
Grant Agreement No.	101069694
Project Start Date	1/06/2022
Project End Date	30/11/2025
Duration	42 months
Website	https://datacellarproject.eu

Deliverable Details

Number	D3.2		
Title	Interactions with other projects dataspaces: how and why - algorithms and architectural approach to be considered in DATA CELLAR CIM		
Work Package	WP3		
Document Nature			
Due Date	31/05/2024 (M24)	Actual Date	28/06/2024 (M25)
Dissemination Level	PU - Public		
Deliverable responsible	CTIC		
Contributing Beneficiaries			
Contributing Author(s)	Andrés García Mangas, CTIC		
Reviewer(s)	Georgios Yiasoumas, FOSS Eric Lambert, EDF		

Document History

Version	Editor(s)	Date	Change Log
v1.0	CTIC	2024-05-01	First complete version (pending review)
v1.1	EDF, FOSS	2024-05-28	Reviews by EDF and FOSS
V1.2	CTIC	2024-06-27	Added new section on the importance of interoperability

Table of contents

List of figures 4

List of abbreviations 5

Executive Summary 6

1. Introduction 7

1.1. Project Summary 7

1.2. Deliverable Scope and Objectives 8

1.3. Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables 8

1.4. Deliverable Structure 9

2. The Importance of Interoperability 10

3. Main Building Blocks of the Connector 12

3.1. IDS Dataspace Protocol 12

3.2. Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) 12

3.3. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) 13

4. Design Decisions 14

4.1. OpenAPI as the Basic Interoperability Component 14

4.2. Connector Service is Distributed as a Container Image 15

4.3. Consumer Applications Decoupled with a Message Broker 15

4.4. Participant Credentials Stored in an OID4VC-compliant Wallet 15

5. Identity and Trust 17

5.1. Verification of Credentials 18

6. Implementation 21

6.1. DATA CELLAR Connector Extensions 21

6.2. Library for Interacting with Connector APIs 21

6.3. Supported Data Transfer Types 22

7. Conclusions 24

List of figures

Figure 1: DATA CELLAR Rationale 7

Figure 2: Relationships with Work Packages..... 9

Figure 3: High-level architecture of a participant’s services 14

Figure 4: Identity and trust diagram..... 17

Figure 5: Structure of the Verifiable Presentations exchanged by connectors 20

Figure 6: Consumer pull data transfer sequence 23

Figure 7: Provider push data transfer sequence 23

List of abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
DID	Decentralized Identifier
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EU	European Union
GXDCH	Gaia-X Digital Clearing House
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS	International Data Spaces
JWS	JSON Web Signature
JWT	JSON Web Token
LECs	Local Energy Communities
OID4VC	OpenID for Verifiable Credentials
OID4VP	OpenID for Verifiable Presentations
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The present deliverable provides a high-level view of the design and development of the DATA CELLAR data space connector, which is one of the main software components required by the DATA CELLAR data space to enable sovereign and interoperable communications between its participants. The DATA CELLAR connector relies on proven technologies of the ecosystem such as the Eclipse Dataspace Components framework, the IDS Dataspace Protocol, and W3C Verifiable Credentials, which minimizes possible risks related to interoperability. The DATA CELLAR connector is currently functional and in an early alpha version and is publicly available on GitHub¹.

¹ <https://github.com/fundacionctic/connector-building-blocks>

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

A greener energy system is crucial for the future prosperity and liveability of European citizens. This requirement is at the heart of the DATA CELLAR approach where Local Energy Communities (LECs) have been recognised by the European Commission as a pivotal measure to play a key role in driving the European Union’s (EU’s) energy transition. At the same time, the digitisation of the EU energy system and the proper exchange of data between energy actors appear crucial to foster the exchange of best practices and the creation of a knowledge community to tackle one of our society’s most pressing global crises: climate change.

Figure 1: DATA CELLAR Rationale

In this context, DATA CELLAR aims to implement a collaborative platform that will provide an interoperable, and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets and AI models to serve and support the spread of energy communities in the European Union, leveraging on experience gained in the development of other EU projects.

DATA CELLAR will create a decentralized data space to store streams or historical data coming from private metering, but it will also provide a data federation integrating data coming from both external companies and EU federation spaces. The data space will be populated by a series of services dedicated to energy utilities, energy communities, private businesses, and citizens. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will provide a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and pre-trained AI models to serve and support LECs.

To achieve its objectives, DATA CELLAR is divided into 9 WPs with different objectives, tasks, and deliverables. This document is contained within WP3, which is focused on liaising with other data space initiatives as well as with other relevant EU and non-EU energy data spaces to connect, share, operate, and deliver. Within WP3, certain architectural design decisions of DATA CELLAR that may impact

interoperability are also considered, as is the case with the DATA CELLAR connector, the focus of this document.

1.2. Deliverable Scope and Objectives

Connectors are one of the main building blocks of data spaces, as described by initiatives such as the International Data Spaces (IDS), to which DATA CELLAR aims to adhere. Connectors serve as the software gateways that facilitate communication and data transfer among participants within a data space. Furthermore, connectors are flexible software components by nature, an important requirement for them to adapt to multiple scenarios such as real-time streaming data or legacy data storage systems. However, this flexibility means that several design decisions need to be made for the connector to reach a functional state that can be deployed and utilized by participants in the data space. Moreover, these design decisions are significant factors influencing technical interoperability with other projects' data spaces: data space connectors that adopt significantly different design choices will encounter technical barriers to exchanging messages and interacting with each other.

This deliverable aims to outline the primary design decisions guiding the development and deployment of the DATA CELLAR data space connector, focusing on interoperability from the perspective of DATA CELLAR participants, as well as considering interoperability with other projects' data spaces. It's important to note that given that other external data spaces are also under development at the time of writing, we cannot strictly guarantee seamless interoperability. To address this, we prioritize the use of widely recognized technologies whenever possible (e.g. IDS Dataspace Protocol) aiming to minimise future interoperability risks.

1.3. Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

The activities in WP3 and WP4 both have a significant impact on the development efforts of the DATA CELLAR data space connector. WP3, responsible for setting the groundwork to ensure interoperability with other EU data spaces, informs the design of the connector to attempt to remove barriers to interoperability. On the other hand, WP4 provides most of the functional and non-functional requirements of the connector software. Moreover, most of the design and development efforts of the connector itself are contained under the umbrella of WP4.

Figure 2: Relationships with Work Packages

1.4. Deliverable Structure

The structure of the remainder of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 provides an overview about the importance of being interoperable
- Section 3 introduces the main building blocks of the connector, that is, the basic technologies and concepts upon which the rest of the components of the connector are developed.
- Section 4 describes the main design decisions taken in the specific context of DATA CELLAR to achieve a functional and complete version of the connector that fulfils all the requirements of the DATA CELLAR data space.
- Section 5 describes the design of DATA CELLAR's approach regarding identity and trust.
- Section 6 includes additional comments related to the software implementation of the design decisions mentioned in the other sections.

2. The Importance of Interoperability

The ability for data ecosystems to interact with one another is crucial to ensure their long-term existence. If we focus on building a single monolithic solution, we risk ending up in the same place we are today, namely a situation where the complex technological challenges of data exchange are being addressed, but significant strategic risks remain due to the high degree of centralization in data platforms. In other words, organizations can exchange data but often depend on private technology giants, which, although crucial players in the ecosystem providing valuable services and resources, could be argued to exert disproportionate central control.

This centralization not only poses risks to data sovereignty but also potentially limits innovation and competition. By diversifying the ecosystem and encouraging interoperability between different data spaces, we can create a more resilient and adaptable data landscape that better serves the needs of various stakeholders, from individual users to large corporations and governments.

The existence of a catalogue of well-known technologies and software projects is key for implementing data spaces effectively. These technologies serve as development building blocks and must be diverse enough to fit various scenarios. It's important that they remain optional and flexible, allowing each data ecosystem to adopt the components necessary for implementing its specific governance and data transfer requirements. This approach enables customization and optimization based on unique use cases, industry needs, or regional regulations.

While this flexibility allows data spaces and ecosystems to maintain a degree of independence, fostering sustainable growth, it's equally important to strike a balance. Data ecosystems should focus on agreeing to a set of interoperable technologies that facilitate collaboration and enable the construction of large-scale data ecosystems composed of other smaller-scale instances. Without this common ground, there's a significant risk of creating isolated data silos with limited growth potential and minimal societal impact.

In other words, the aim could be to reach a compromise between full centralization, which can simplify interoperability, and fully autonomous and disconnected data ecosystems, which increase sovereignty.

This document aims to explain the design decisions adopted by the DATA CELLAR data space to create a sovereign data space while keeping interoperability in mind, always striving to reuse well-known and proven technologies in the data space ecosystem.

With the term "interoperability", we refer to the possibility of separate data spaces to interact with each other's datasets and services without severe technological barriers that demand a large investment of development resources to produce bespoke adapters or communication gateways. Some degree of development for adaptation is to be expected; that is, seamless interoperability, including semantic interoperability and data transfer technology interoperability, is not the expected outcome. The idea is for data spaces to be designed around the same principles and open-source ecosystems, so that seamless interoperability is only a couple of steps away and can be implemented with a reasonable amount of resources if necessary.

In the context of the projects developing the Common European Energy Data Space (CEEDS), including DATA CELLAR, it is even more important to agree on interoperability guidelines and clearly

communicate implementation decisions that affect the ability of these energy data spaces to interact with each other. This document also aims to describe these implementation decisions from a high-level perspective for easy comprehension, while providing specific and technical details to give actionable information to DATA CELLAR's partners.

Specifically, the following questions related to interoperability-relevant design decisions in the context of DATA CELLAR's software ecosystem are addressed at some level:

- What are the main open-source software frameworks that DATA CELLAR's implementation is based on?
- What's the protocol used in the data space for managing contract negotiation and data transfer processes?
- How are data space participants identified? How are authorization checks implemented to check if a participant can access an offer from another participant?
- What are the software services that DATA CELLAR expects each participant of the data space to have in their own infrastructure?
- Has DATA CELLAR developed any bespoke software components that may be differentiating factors? How are they organized?

3. Main Building Blocks of the Connector

3.1. IDS Dataspace Protocol

According to the International Data Spaces (IDS) Dataspace Protocol specification²:

The Dataspace Protocol is a set of specifications designed to facilitate interoperable data sharing between entities governed by usage control and based on Web technologies. These specifications define the schemas and protocols required for entities to publish data, negotiate Agreements, and access data as part of a federation of technical systems termed a Dataspace.

In other words, the Dataspace Protocol is the common language agreed upon by participants of the data space to express dataset offerings, manage the contract negotiation process, and lay the groundwork for data transfer before delegating to actual data transfer mechanisms, which fall outside the scope of the Dataspace Protocol.

This last detail is something important to consider: the Dataspace Protocol is concerned with managing the data transfer process at a high level (e.g., how the provider signals the consumer to indicate that the transfer has terminated), but the specifics of how the data is moved between participants (e.g., via HTTP, S3 protocol, by pushing a file to an SFTP server) are left to the implementer.

The Dataspace Protocol defines three main protocol specifications to achieve these goals:

- The **Catalog Protocol** defines how *Catalogs* and *Datasets* are requested from *Catalog Services*. It also specifies that *Catalogs* are instances of the DCAT vocabulary *Catalog* class and *Datasets* are instances of DCAT *Datasets*. Additionally, it imposes certain requirements on how these DCAT entities need to be constructed.
- The **Contract Negotiation Protocol** defines the state machine and related transition messages that both the provider and consumer need to implement for an *Agreement* between both parties to be reached so that the *Datasets* involved in the transaction can proceed to the data transfer phase.
- The **Transfer Process Protocol** introduces the concepts of the data plane and the control plane. On the control plane, this protocol defines a state machine and related transition messages for the provider and consumer to manage the state of the data transfer (e.g., a transfer process can be “started” or “suspended”). On the data plane, the actual data transmission takes place, which is, as mentioned before, outside the scope of the Dataspace Protocol.

3.2. Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC)

The Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) is an ecosystem of software components, among which an implementation of a data space connector compliant with the IDS Dataspace Protocol is the most significant.

² <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/dataspace-protocol/>

The EDC connector software ecosystem serves as the fundamental foundation upon which DATA CELLAR's connector is built.

The EDC connector is developed with extensibility and flexibility as key driving principles. It offers a core set of functionalities and exposes a variety of extensions to achieve the mentioned flexibility. For instance, there are extensions that implement authentication based on OAuth2, as well as others that support various technologies for data transmission, such as S3 or HTTP.

3.3. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI)

Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) fundamentally changes the management of digital identity by providing individuals or organizations with full control over their personal data, removing the reliance on intermediaries or centralized authorities. These central authorities are present in almost all scenarios in the current Web landscape; examples of well-known central identity providers include government authorities and technology businesses such as Google and Microsoft.

Key to SSI are principles of user control, privacy preservation, and avoiding vendor lock-in due to proprietary technologies or services. With SSI, users have the ultimate say over their digital identities, determining what information to disclose and to whom. This change of approach to identity empowers users and could reduce the risk of data breaches and identity theft.

The building blocks of SSI are mainly two: Decentralized Identifiers (DID) and Verifiable Credentials (VC):

Decentralized Identifiers (DID) are globally unique identifiers that are cryptographically verifiable and, as mentioned before, not dependent on a central authority. A DID is essentially a string that points to a public key, uniquely identifying an individual or organization, such as "did:example:a1b2c3", where the second part ("example") indicates the method used by this DID, and the third part ("a1b2c3") is the globally unique identifier specific to the method. It's important to note that various methods exist for DIDs; each method defines how a DID is registered and resolved, including how it's stored in the *verifiable data registry* and how its details can be obtained by any actor. For instance, some DID methods leverage the integrity guarantees of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), while others serialize identity details directly into the DID URL itself, effectively removing the need for an external verifiable data registry.

Verifiable Credentials (VC) are machine-readable documents that essentially contain claims about an individual or organization. For example, a VC could include a claim that an organization is a non-governmental organization, serving the same function as it being listed in a central physical register managed by a national authority. Like DIDs, VCs are cryptographically verifiable, ensuring that any actor can confirm the VC hasn't been tampered with or compromised. Trust is placed in the cryptographic techniques used for proof generation and verification, which are secure and resistant to attacks. The relationship between DID and VC is that VC is bound to DID and describes characteristics of the subject's identity. DIDs identify who someone is, while VCs provide additional information about that individual or organization.

4. Design Decisions

DATA CELLAR's connector is built on top of the main building blocks outlined in Section 2. These blocks heavily influence both the operation and development of DATA CELLAR's specific configuration of the connector. Nonetheless, there are still significant and specific open points that must be addressed before arriving at a runnable and fully functional version of the connector software service. These design decisions are described in this section.

Figure 3 shows a diagram that identifies the components in the internal infrastructure of each data space participant. The diagram reflects the design decisions discussed below.

Figure 3: High-level architecture of a participant's services

4.1. OpenAPI as the Basic Interoperability Component

OpenAPI is a specification for building and documenting HTTP APIs. It defines a data model for describing functionalities, parameters, and data serialization formats, enabling developers to understand how to interact with APIs while promoting reusability of terms and concepts across different APIs. OpenAPI has a healthy ecosystem of related tools that can assist with tasks such as automatically generating client code or documentation sites. It has evolved to arguably become a de facto standard for HTTP APIs.

It is expected that the infrastructure, services, and datasets of different participants will vary greatly. DATA CELLAR's proposal to address this heterogeneity is for each participant to expose its internal datasets and services via an HTTP API described using OpenAPI. The rationale for this decision is mainly based on the popularity of HTTP APIs and the OpenAPI specification: it is reasonable to expect a wide array of developers with different technology stacks to be able to develop a wrapper HTTP API to provide access to these datasets and services. In other words, it's challenging to suggest an alternative technology to HTTP APIs that is better documented and has such a large ecosystem of tools.

The connector would then parse the OpenAPI schema file of the wrapper API to identify which assets need to be exposed to the data space and how they can be accessed via HTTP requests.

This approach represents a reasonable compromise between the effort required on the participant's side and the impracticality of the connector having an ad-hoc extension to adapt to each specific case.

4.2. Connector Service is Distributed as a Container Image

The data space participants should not need to be deeply familiar with the inner workings and low-level details of what the connector is and how it behaves. The objective is for the data space connector to act as a black box service that takes a properties configuration file and then can run mostly unattended. This does not mean that participants would not have access to low-level configuration if needed: participants with the appropriate skillset would be able to deploy bespoke versions of the connector if they deem it necessary; however, for participants who do not have the resources to invest in training to learn the particularities of DATA CELLAR's connector, the service will aim to minimize the required investment.

To facilitate the deployment process, DATA CELLAR's connector will be published as a public container image in a popular and well-known image repository such as Docker Hub. The documentation will aim to reduce the time from first contact with the connector to a working version being deployed and functional.

4.3. Consumer Applications Decoupled with a Message Broker

Interactions in the data space are asynchronous in nature: there may be unexpected latencies, each participant's infrastructure and internal protocols are different, and messages can be lost. It is necessary for the data space connector to operate in an asynchronous fashion to accommodate this principle. This means that consumer applications—applications that connect to the data space via a data space connector to browse catalogues, download assets, or access services—need to be able to operate by reacting to asynchronous events. Specifically, these asynchronous messages are responses from the provider's side, which may contain the actual desired data or an access token along with details to obtain the desired data.

In the case of DATA CELLAR's connector, RabbitMQ was chosen as the tool to decouple the messages received by the consumer and enable consumer applications to subscribe to and process them asynchronously. RabbitMQ was selected due to its popularity and ease of use as a message broker. Other approximately equivalent options, such as Redis, could have been chosen as well. Moreover, it's worth noting that a message broker is not strictly necessary: any mechanism capable of passing the messages received on the connector to the application would be suitable. Nevertheless, RabbitMQ is a stable and well-known software service, undoubtedly one of the choices with the lowest risks.

4.4. Participant Credentials Stored in an OID4VC-compliant Wallet

OpenID for Verifiable Credentials and OpenID for Verifiable Presentations (OID4VC and OID4VP, respectively) are sets of specifications proposing mechanisms for the issuance, presentation, and exchange of Verifiable Credentials (VC). Built upon the existing OpenID Connect flows and concepts, these specifications facilitate the implementation of SSI (Self-Sovereign Identity) while minimizing development efforts, leveraging existing knowledge and infrastructure related to OpenID Connect.

The connector for the DATA CELLAR data space will be developed with the aim of leveraging OID4VC and OID4VP wherever possible. The rationale is to avoid making specific design choices that could compromise interoperability with external data spaces by adopting a specification that has traction in the ecosystem. However, it should be noted that both OID4VC and OID4VP are still in an early stage, and there are associated risks related to their lack of maturity.

5. Identity and Trust

This section describes how credentials are issued and exchanged within the data space, either automatically between connectors during a communication session, or between participants and authorities in DATA CELLAR.

Figure 4 shows a diagram depicting the basic actors and components, illustrating the issuance of credentials and their flow between data space connectors. Several key details can be extracted from the figure, as explained in the following paragraphs.

Figure 4: Identity and trust diagram

This strategy implements authentication within the DATA CELLAR data space. Verifiable Credentials and Verifiable Presentations, along with their associated cryptographic operations, are used by

participants to prove their identity in the data space. This also enables other participants to confirm permissions.

The identity and trust architecture leverages the walt.id Wallet and Issuer APIs. The walt.id³ is a software ecosystem that provides software libraries, APIs, and web applications to manage the lifecycle of the building blocks of SSI, most importantly cryptographic keys, DIDs, and Verifiable Credentials. One of its most interesting features is that the provided APIs—the Issuer API, the Verifier API, and the Wallet API—implement the OID4VC and OID4VP specifications, which are particularly useful for DATA CELLAR's case. More specifically, the Wallet API allows participants to store and manage cryptographic keys, DIDs, and credentials. The Issuer API can issue credentials that are then accepted by the Wallet via OID4VC, and the Verifier API implements the logic to verify presentations via OID4VP. While the integration of the Verifier API and OID4VP protocol is planned, it is not depicted in the current diagram. This omission is because connectors need to establish a bidirectional communication channel to implement the flow of an OID4VP presentation request and fulfilment. For now, an alternative solution involves a connector directly presenting the credentials to the counterparty without requiring the counterparty to first generate a presentation request.

The process of onboarding a participant to the data space involves the DATA CELLAR administrators sending a new issuance request to the Security Module API, which serves as the central entry point to DATA CELLAR's identity and trust services. This issuance request generates an OID4VC credential offer URL, which is then transferred to the participant. This URL enables the participant to accept the credentials and store them in their Wallet. Currently, plans include developing a companion web application to facilitate participants in accepting the credential offer URL. However, participants always retain control and have the option to utilize other applications or tools if necessary.

Given that one of DATA CELLAR's primary requirements is compliance with Gaia-X, the Verifiable Credentials issued to participants must adhere to the Gaia-X Credentials data model. These credentials need to be submitted to an instance of the Gaia-X Digital Clearing House for the Gaia-X Compliance API to issue cryptographic proofs of Gaia-X compliance.

Another key decision is that DATA CELLAR will utilize the DID web method. The rationale behind this decision is that the DID web method offers adequate sovereignty guarantees and is arguably simpler to comprehend and manage for participants within the data space compared to other DID methods based on DLTs. While there are simpler DID methods available (e.g., key method), these pose challenges with key revocation. Therefore, the DID web method is considered a suitable compromise.

5.1. Verification of Credentials

The credentials exchanged between connectors are not credentials in the strict sense; they are Verifiable Presentations containing at least one Verifiable Credential. These presentations must fulfil all the following requirements:

1. These presentations must be issued (i.e., signed) by the same DID that serves as both the holder and subject of the presentation.

³ <https://walt.id/identity-infrastructure>

2. The subjects of all credentials in the presentation must be the same DID as the issuer of the presentation.
3. All credentials must be issued by the DID of one of the trust anchors of the DATA CELLAR data space.

The signature of the presentation proves that the holder of the credentials was the originator of the presentation. The signature of the credentials proves that the holder (i.e. the presenter) has been verified and vetted by the DATA CELLAR central services. This approach ensures that a potentially malicious third party cannot present a credential of which it is not the legitimate owner.

Moreover, since the presentations are serialized in the form of JSON Web Tokens (JWT) that are, in turn, encoded as JSON Web Signatures (JWS), the inherent features of these technologies can be utilized to enhance the integrity and security of the presentation:

- The *audience* claim is checked by the recipient of the presentation to match its own identity. This identity can take the form of, for example, the DID or the Protocol API URL of the connector.
- The *expiration time* claim must be set in the immediate future, typically a few minutes, to minimize the window during which a malicious third party who gains access to the JWT can exploit it.

Verifiable Credentials serialized as JWTs are sometimes referred to as VC-JWT, while Verifiable Presentations are indicated as VP-JWT.

It is important to note that, at the time of writing, replay attacks are still a risk in this design due to the absence of a nonce in the presentation. A nonce is a random fragment that is communicated by the recipient of the presentation to the presenter so that the presenter can include it in the JWT and then sign it. The recipient of the presentation knows that any JWT that does not match the nonce should not be accepted, even if the presentation has been signed by the expected presenter. This issue will be addressed at a later stage in a future release of the connector software.

The following diagram (Figure 5) shows a high-level view of the structure of the Verifiable Presentations exchanged by connectors, which contain the Verifiable Credentials that are checked on each exchange to verify that the counterparty is authorized.

Figure 5: Structure of the Verifiable Presentations exchanged by connectors

6. Implementation

The software that implements the design decisions described in this document is publicly available on GitHub⁴. It is recommended to check that repository for the latest examples and updates on the development of DATA CELLAR's connector. The following sections provide additional commentary on the particularities of the implementation.

6.1. DATA CELLAR Connector Extensions

DATA CELLAR adopts the extension-based architecture of the EDC connector. Therefore, all the bespoke functionality of the DATA CELLAR connector that is not present in the original EDC connector codebase is implemented as an extension. Specifically, there are two extensions at the time of writing:

- An EDC connector extension capable of interpreting an OpenAPI schema and generating a set of datasets within the data space to represent the services provided by a participant component. The underlying idea is to enable participants to develop their own HTTP APIs while the extension abstracts away the intricacies of exposing these HTTP APIs to the data space. The only interface that must be respected by the participant is strict adherence to the OpenAPI schema of their HTTP APIs.
- An EDC connector extension that implements authentication via Verifiable Credentials. This extension contains logic to interact with the API of the wallet service. The extension can search for credentials in the wallet and then build the associated Verifiable Presentation. It also contains the logic to parse and validate the presentation according to the requirements described in Section 5.1.

6.2. Library for Interacting with Connector APIs

The APIs of the EDC connector involve complex interactions with multiple requests. Progressing through the state machines of the contract negotiation and transfer process flows requires sending several HTTP requests to these APIs, handling the possible errors and edge cases. To facilitate this process, DATA CELLAR is currently developing a library written in Python named **edcpy**.

The edcpy library serves to encapsulate this logic, making it reusable. Additionally, it provides an implementation of a *consumer backend* that integrates with RabbitMQ.

It should be noted that a *consumer backend* has a specific meaning in this context. The *consumer backend* is a service within the participant's infrastructure that has two primary responsibilities:

- In the consumer pull transfer pattern, it receives the access token from the provider side. This object contains details on how and where to send the HTTP request to obtain the final response.
- In the provider push transfer pattern, it receives the actual final response.

A *consumer backend* implementation is provided out-of-the-box by the edcpy library. It is not necessary for each participant to develop their own version; the same implementation can be reused across the data space.

⁴ <https://github.com/fundacionctic/connector-building-blocks>

However, it's important to note that the use of Python is not mandatory. The edcpy library is designed to hopefully facilitate the development process, but if participants prefer to use another programming language, they have the flexibility to build their own *consumer backend* and directly communicate with the connector APIs.

Minimal example of the edcpy library

```
from edcpy.edc_api import ConnectorController

async def main():
    """List the datasets available in the Provider's catalogue."""

    logger = logging.getLogger(__name__)
    counter_party_protocol_url: str = "http://provider.local:9194/protocol"
    controller = ConnectorController()

    catalog = await controller.fetch_catalog(
        counter_party_protocol_url=counter_party_protocol_url
    )

    logger.info("Found datasets:\n%s", pprint.pformat(list(catalog.datasets)))
```

6.3. Supported Data Transfer Types

The connector of DATA CELLAR implements the two types of data transfer specified by the Transfer Data Plane EDC extension. The following two figures illustrate the sequence of interactions between a consumer connector and a provider connector in these two types of data transfers.

Figure 6 depicts the *consumer pull* pattern, where the consumer application receives an access token, allowing direct access to the backend HTTP API through the provider connector acting as a proxy. In this case, a single access token can be reused to send multiple requests to the same HTTP endpoint with different body contents and query arguments, which may prove more optimal depending on the size and rate of requests.

Figure 6: Consumer pull data transfer sequence

Figure 7 illustrates the *provider push* pattern, where the provider connector sends the response directly to the consumer backend without involving the consumer connector. This requires exposing the consumer backend to the Internet, an important consideration when planning to support the provider push transfer pattern.

Figure 7: Provider push data transfer sequence

7. Conclusions

The software ecosystem in the data spaces domain evolves at a fairly fast pace. There are multiple promising projects that, although not stable at the moment, could prove instrumental in building data spaces in the near future. DATA CELLAR has adopted two of the most popular building blocks in this regard: The Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) framework and Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI).

DATA CELLAR is prioritizing the development of a stable early version of its software services to establish a functional data space as quickly as possible. The minimum viable product encompasses a set of basic requirements, primarily focused on securely exchanging datasets between participants with an acceptable level of trust. While more advanced features may be added as the project evolves, they are not the primary focus at this stage.

All the design decisions described in this document have been adopted with the fundamental requirement of minimizing the risk to interoperability, both within the broader ecosystem of data spaces and specifically with DATA CELLAR's sister projects. While certain development decisions may not immediately enable out-of-the-box interoperability with all projects, it can be argued that DATA CELLAR's building blocks do not pose a significant barrier to interoperability. Interoperability could be achieved with a limited amount of effort by developing new extensions or simple adapters.

Finally, it's worth noting that the software implementation of DATA CELLAR's connector is publicly available online for reuse within the ecosystem, with the hope that it will accelerate the adoption of data space technologies.